

Shear Force Resistance of Plate Girders with Trapezoidally Corrugated Webs and Reinforced Web Openings

Jian Wang^{*,a}, Zheng Li^b, Mathias Euler^a

^aBrandenburg University of Technology, Chair of Steel and Timber Structures, Germany
Jian.Wang@b-tu.de, Mathias.Euler@b-tu.de

^bTechnical University of Berlin, Department of Steel Structure, Germany
Zheng.Li@tu-berlin.de

ABSTRACT

Corrugated web beams are an alternative to steel girders with flat webs. They consist of a welded I-section with a thin-walled trapezoidally corrugated web and flanges made of wide flat steel. In comparison with hot-rolled or welded I-beams with flat webs, corrugated web beams offer significant material savings and are produced fully automated. Assuming the same load-bearing capacity, corrugated web beams are lighter than those with a flat web, since the corrugated web beams can often be loaded up to their plastic resistance without reinforcement of the web. Research on the load-bearing behaviour of corrugated web beams without web openings is well-established. However, the resistance of corrugated web beams with reinforced web openings, which are necessary for installations in buildings, has not been well investigated experimentally yet. This paper examines the shear force resistance of trapezoidally corrugated web beams with reinforced square web openings. Two beam-like specimens with the same geometry but differently reinforced web openings were tested. The experimental results are compared with a Finite Element Analysis using Abaqus® and with an analytical model that allows a simplified calculation. The comparison identifies how the wall thickness of the web opening reinforcement affects the shear force resistance of perforated corrugated web beams.

Keywords: shear force resistance, trapezoidally corrugated webs, reinforced web openings

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

In industrial and other engineering structures, the integration of ventilation, heating, water supply, and similar pipelines requires the creation of openings in steel girder with corrugated webs as shown in *Fig. 1b*. However, these openings can lead to stress concentrations, resulting in significantly increased stresses compared to the "average stresses" of unperforated corrugated webs. This stress concentration forms a significant risk to the structural integrity and may result in structural failure. To mitigate this risk, it is common practice to reinforce the opening by adding circumferential stiffeners as shown in *Fig. 1d*. This approach aims to reduce the stress concentration around the openings to ensure the structural stability and integrity of the steel girder.

1.2 State of the art

In recent decades, there have been numerous experimental and numerical investigations focused on trapezoidally corrugated web girders (TCWG) with circular web openings. In 1994, Lindner and Huang (1) investigated TCWG with circular cut-outs as shown in *Fig. 1b*. The investigation focused on the local buckling behaviour of TCWG with unreinforced web openings, using both experimental and numerical methods. The tension field method of (2) for flat webs with unreinforced cut-outs (see *Fig. 1a*) has been adapted for TCWG with web openings. A corrected buckling coefficient has been introduced accounting for the web corrugation and the following two cases: (i) The cut-out is

completely located within a subpanel of the corrugated web as shown in *Fig. 1b*, (ii) the cut-out includes the edge of two adjacent subpanels of the corrugated web.

Fig. 1. Steel girders with web openings: a) flat web, b) trapezoidally corrugated web; types of web opening: c) unreinforced cut-out, d) reinforced web opening

In 2009, Romeijn et al. (3) conducted a parametric study on steel girders with trapezoidal corrugated webs and circular web openings using finite element analysis, building on Lindner's research. A refined buckling coefficient has been developed that proposes a linear dependency on the diameter of the cut-out. The local buckling coefficient of the perforated corrugated web turns out to be more influenced by the diameter and horizontal eccentricity of the cut-out than by the depth of the web. However, only web openings completely located within a subpanel of the corrugated web were investigated, which restricts the design proposal in size and location of the web opening.

In 2018, Li and Qiu (4) investigated the buckling mode of the trapezoidally corrugated web girder with unreinforced circular web openings, using both experimental and numerical methods. In contrast to (1), their study focused on large openings that include an edge of two adjacent subpanels of the corrugated web. Based on a parametric study (finite element analysis), a design formula to calculate the critical shear stress has been proposed.

In 2022, Tohamy et al. (5) performed tests on TCWG with unreinforced rectangular cut-outs, see *Fig. 1c*. To the best of the authors' knowledge, trapezoidally corrugated web girders with reinforced rectangular web openings as shown in see *Fig. 1d* have not been the subject of research up to now.

2 THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

This section considers webs of TCWG that are only subject to shear forces, as commonly assumed by EN 1993-1-5, Annex D (6). When analysing corrugated webs with reinforced web openings, it is important to take into account two possible failure mechanisms: (i) failure of the corrugated web, (ii) failure of the web opening reinforcement (circumferential stiffener in *Fig. 1d*). This approach has been proposed by Robra and Krasotina in (7) for sinusoidally corrugated webs with openings.

The shear force resistance, $V_{Rd,1}$, for the failure of the trapezoidally corrugated web can be determined according to (6) as follows:

$$V_{Rd,1} = V_{bw,Rd} = \frac{\chi_c f_{y,w} h_w t_w}{\gamma_{M1} \sqrt{3}} \quad (1)$$

where h_w is the web depth, t_w is the web thickness, $f_{y,w}$ is the yield strength of the web, and γ_{M1} is the partial factor. The reduction factor χ_c is determined according to (6) and is the smaller one of the reduction factors for local and global shear buckling of the web.

To determine the shear force resistance, $V_{Rd,2}$, for the failure of the web opening reinforcement, the rectangular cross-section of the circumferential stiffener in *Fig. 1d* is considered as a closed frame as shown in *Fig. 2a*. The internal forces (M , N , V) in the frame, that are caused by a constant shear flow q

are calculated. In the following, it is assumed that the bending moment is the primary stressing of the frame, and the normal and shear forces are negligible.

Fig. 2. Circumferential stiffener treated as frame: a) geometry and loading, b) deformation under constant shear flow, c) bending moment diagram, d) 3D illustration

The maximum bending moment in the reinforcement as shown in *Fig. 2c* is obtained as follows (8):

$$M_{\max} = 0,25 q b_1 b_2 \quad (2)$$

where b_1 and b_2 are the cross-sectional dimensions of the web opening reinforcement, see *Fig. 2a*, and q is the shear flow in the girder web. In the limit state, the reinforcement yields and the maximum bending moment reaches the value of the plastic moment of the stiffener wall:

$$M_{pl,r} = 0,25 t_r^2 b_r f_{y,r} / \gamma_M = 0,25 q b_1 b_2 \quad (3)$$

where b_r is the depth of the stiffener (*Fig. 2d*), $f_{y,r}$ is the yield strength of the stiffener, and γ_M is the partial factor. For simplicity, γ_M is set to γ_{M1} in the following. By rearranging and simplifying of *Eq. (3)*, the maximum shear flow in the girder web can be calculated as follows:

$$q_{Rd} = \frac{t_r^2 b_r f_{y,r}}{b_1 b_2 \gamma_{M1}} \quad (4)$$

The shear force resistance, $V_{Rd,2}$, is finally obtained when the constant shear flow is integrated over the web depth h_w :

$$V_{Rd,2} = q_{Rd} h_w = \frac{t_r^2 b_r f_{y,r}}{b_1 b_2 \gamma_{M1}} h_w \quad (5)$$

Finally, the shear force resistance of the TCWG with reinforced web opening is obtain as:

$$V_{Rd} = \min \begin{cases} V_{Rd,1} & \text{local or global web buckling} \\ V_{Rd,2} & \text{plastic failure of stiffener} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

For design purposes, the reinforcement of a web opening should not reduce the shear force resistance of the TCWG. Therefore, $V_{Rd,2} \geq V_{Rd,1}$ should apply. That leads to following relationship:

$$\frac{b_1 b_2}{t_r^2} \leq \frac{b_r f_{y,r} \sqrt{3}}{\chi_c f_{y,w} t_w} \quad (7)$$

Moreover, the relationship is further simplified in case of a square web opening ($b = b_1 = b_2$):

$$\frac{b}{t_r} \leq 1.316 \sqrt{\frac{b_r f_{y,r}}{\chi_c f_{y,w} t_w}} \quad (8)$$

where b is the dimension of the web opening.

3 EXPERIMENT INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Test specimens

Two test specimens were fully automatically fabricated under manufacturing conditions to investigate the shear buckling behaviour of TCWG with reinforced square web openings. The beam length measured 1950 mm allowing a span of 1935 mm for the tests. The dimensions of the flanges and stiffeners and the span-to-width ratio of the test specimens were chosen in such a way that web failure under shear stresses was induced. As a result, all tested beams were stocky.

All test specimens had flanges with dimensions of 250×15 mm to prevent local buckling in the upper flange caused by compression forces and to withstand yielding in the bottom flange under tensile forces. The corrugated web consisted of a trapezoidal profile with a nominal thickness of 2 mm. The dimensions of the corrugation are shown in Fig. 3. The corrugation angle is 45° .

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of corrugated web beam specimen

Table 1 summarizes the dimensions of the test specimens. The web height h_w amounted to 500 mm for both specimens. Flat transverse stiffeners with a thickness of 15 mm were placed in the region of load introduction and at the supports to prevent local web buckling. Thus, the transverse stiffener at midspan divided the corrugated web into two equal parts each connected to the flanges and the transverse stiffeners by single fillet welds with a throat thickness of about 3 mm.

Table 1. Dimensions of test specimens [mm]

No.	Web height	Stiffener around the web opening		Dimension of web opening	
	h_w	t_r	b_r	B (outer dimension)	$b = B - t_r$
1	500	6	150	212	206
2	500	15	150	232	217

The square web openings in Fig. 3 had outer dimensions B of 212 mm for specimen #1 and 232 mm for specimen #2, which corresponded to almost half the web height. The openings were cut into the web plate automatically using plasma cutting.

The circumference of each web cut-out was reinforced by flat plates serving as stiffeners. The circumferential stiffeners were connected to the web plate by a double fillet welds with a throat

thickness of 3 mm. The depth b_r of the web opening stiffeners measured 150 mm for all specimens, resulting in a ratio of b_r/B approximately equal to 0.7. The web openings were positioned at the centre of each beam half.

3.2 Material properties

The test specimens were made of structural steel having different steel grades. For a more precise numerical analysis of the test specimens, the material properties of the steels were determined from tensile tests with flat and round samples. Since the thickness of the corrugated web was only 2 mm, flat samples according to DIN 50125 (9) were chosen. Round samples according to (9) were chosen for the web opening stiffeners because of the greater plate thickness. Three samples were tested for each component.

Based on the tensile tests, Young's modulus was approximately 200 GPa for both specimens and their components. The true stress-strain relationships were determined according to EN 1993-1-5, Annex C (6) from the engineering stress-strain curve of the tensile tests. *Table 2* shows the true stress-strain relationship of specimen #2. The yield strength of the web and stiffeners were 290 MPa and 320 MPa for specimen #1 and 290 MPa and 280 MPa for specimen #2.

Table 2. True stress-strain relationships of specimen #2

Plastic strain [-]		0.00	0.02	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
Stress [MPa]	Stiffener	280	290	340	375	390	410
	Web	290	293	355	406	438	462

3.3 Experimental setup

The specimens were tested under three-point bending as shown in *Fig. 4*. The vertical force was applied by a hydraulic cylinder, denoted as '2' in *Fig. 4*, and concentrically introduced as line load into the specimen through the transverse stiffener ('4') at midspan.

Legend

- 1 – supports
- 2 – hydraulic cylinder
- 3 – strain gauges
- 4 – transverse stiffener at loading section
- 5 – transducer for vertical displacement u_z

Fig. 4. Experimental setup of specimen #1

The test set-up was statically determinate since lubricant at the supports, denoted as '1' in *Fig. 4*, prevented horizontal support actions. Transducers were arranged on both sides of the load introduction stiffener and measured the vertical displacements u_z (deflection) of the bottom flange. Additionally, two transducers were attached to the top flange and the bottom flange to record the lateral displacements of the test specimen.

3.4 Test results

Fig. 5 indicates the failure mode of the tested specimens after testing. Obviously, the test specimens failed more or less in a similar way. All buckles were induced by shear stresses, ran at an angle and were directed to the loading sections at midspan.

Fig. 5. Ultimate forces $F_z = F_{ult}$ and observed failure modes after testing: a) specimen #1, b) specimen #2

Fig. 6 shows the load-displacement curves of specimens #1 and #2. The curves exhibit a nearly linear behaviour until reaching approximately 80% of the ultimate load. As the ultimate load is approached, the slope of the curves decreases in a non-linear manner. The web region in vicinity of the web opening corner experiences the highest Von Mises stresses according to the numerical calculations.

Fig. 6. Load-displacement curves of specimens #1 and #2

The web opening reinforcement of both specimens was relatively thick-walled compared to the thin corrugated web ($t_w = 2$ mm). The only possible failure mode for specimen #2 with the heaviest web opening reinforcement was local shear buckling of the web. In contrast, the web opening reinforcement of specimen #1 deformed plastically before local web buckling was initiated under shear. Thus, the visible plastic deformations of the web opening reinforcement, that means the

circumferential stiffeners, were comparatively large for specimen #1 and comparatively small for specimen #2, compare *Figs. 5a* and *b*. Besides the plastically deformed web opening reinforcement, shear buckles are visible in *Fig. 5*. The phenomenon of the shear buckles that spread over multiple waves is known as post-buckling.

The ultimate load of specimen #2 is approximately 30% higher than that of specimen #1. This increase can be attributed to the thicker web opening reinforcement of specimen #2. For the tested specimens, increasing the wall-thickness of the web opening stiffeners by a factor of 1.5 resulted in a 30% increase in load-bearing capacity.

4 NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS AND COMPARISON WITH TESTS

4.1 Finite element analysis

The specimens are numerically investigated by a finite element analysis (FEA) using the software package Abaqus®. The tested specimens are simulated with their geometric dimensions according to *Fig. 3* and *Table 1*. The material properties of the FE model are based on the material characterization according to *Table 2*. Four-node shell elements (S4R) are applied for all components to mesh the generated geometry. A minimum element size of 5 mm is used based on the outcome of a prior sensitivity study. The boundary conditions are shown in *Fig. 7* and correspond to the experiments. The analysis method GMNIA according to EN 1993-1-5 (6) is used.

Fig. 7. Finite element model of specimen #1 with boundary conditions and loading

Fig. 8. First Eigenmode from LBA of specimen #2

The FEA takes into account equivalent imperfections based on equivalent deformations affine to the first Eigenmode shape. To determine the first Eigenmode shape, a linear bifurcation analysis (LBA) is performed. *Fig. 8* shows the first Eigenmode of specimen #2 as an example, which is associated with local buckling in a subpanel of the corrugated web.

For analysis purposes, the maximum amplitude of the first Eigenmode is scaled to $e_0 = h_w/200 = 2.5$ mm according to EN 1993-1-5 (6). It should be noted that the maximum amplitude proposed by (6) is only applicable to flat webs. There are currently no proposals for corrugated webs. Additionally, two other imperfections with a maximum amplitude $e_0 = 1$ mm and $e_0 = t_w = 2.0$ mm are investigated. Residual stresses are not considered by the FEA. Any imperfection of the stiffeners is neglected.

Fig. 9b shows the experimental and numerical load-displacement curves of the specimen #2. The curves show a good fit between the FEA and the test results in the elastic deformation range from $u_z = 0$ mm to 4 mm. When approaching the ultimate load, the results of the FEA slightly deviate from the test results. After reaching the ultimate load, all numerical simulations exhibit the typical sudden decrease in load. For specimen #1, the differently defined imperfections have only a minor effect on the ultimate load, as visible in *Fig. 9a*, because this specimen failed due to yielding of the web opening reinforcement.

Fig. 9. Load-displacement curve from tests and FEA

Fig. 10. Von Mises stresses – specimen #1: a) ultimate load level, b) load level corresponding with $u_z = 15$ mm; – specimen #2: c) ultimate load level, d) load level corresponding with $u_z = 15$ mm (unscaled deformations)

Fig. 10 shows the von Mises stresses of both specimens at different loading levels taking into account imperfections with a maximum amplitude $e_0 = t_w$. At ultimate load level, the FE stresses in Fig. 10a show stress concentrations in the web along the vertical edges of the web opening for specimen #1 that are caused by plastic deformation of the web opening reinforcement. In contrast, the FE stresses in the web of Fig. 10c have a more or less uniform stress pattern when approaching the bifurcation point. Obviously, the web stress distribution is not disturbed by the web opening.

The post-buckling behaviour (Figs. 10b and d) predicted by the FEA corresponds well with the test observations (Fig. 5). During post-buckling, the FE stresses in Fig. 10b indicate the presence of several local shear buckles for specimen #1. For specimen #2, the FE stresses in Fig. 10d predict a single global shear buckle.

In summary, specimen #2 is more sensitive to geometric imperfections, as it fails due to shear buckling of the web. Neglecting imperfections in the FEA can lead to an overestimation of the actual ultimate load by up to 10%. In contrast, the failure of specimen #1 at a comparatively lower ultimate load is controlled by yielding of the web opening reinforcement and, therefore, not affected by imperfections of the web.

4.2 Comparative consideration

Fig. 11 compares the shear forces resistances obtained from the tests with those predicted by the FEA and the analytical model from Section 2. In addition, the shear force resistance of an unperforated TCWG is calculated according to EN 1993-1-5, Annex D (6) that amounts to $V_{Rk} = 97,1$ kN. The test result of specimen #1 clearly illustrates that EN 1993-1-5 is not applicable for TCWG with web openings and thin-walled reinforcements. For specimen #2, EN 1993-1-5 gives conservative results as the reinforcement of the web opening is so heavy that it does not affect the buckling resistance of the web.

The comparison with the results from FEA illustrates that the solution of the analytical model is always conservative, but also less economical. A wall thickness of $t_r \approx 14$ mm of the reinforcement is necessary according to the analytical model to achieve the shear force resistance of the unperforated web, while a wall thickness of $t_r \approx 9$ mm is already sufficient according to the FEA in the considered case. It is assumed that the deviation between the FEA and the analytical model, especially for thin-walled web opening reinforcements, is caused by the neglected contribution of the flanges due to the *Vierendeel* mechanism.

Fig. 11. Comparison of tested shear resistances of specimen #1 and #2 with the analytical model in Section 2 and the FEA in Section 4

5 SUMMARY

The results of an investigation on the shear force behaviour of trapezoidally corrugated web girders (TCWG) with differently reinforced square web openings were presented. The outcome of ultimate load tests on two test specimens and of corresponding numerical calculations was described. The

specimens were numerically analysed with the analysis method GMNIA using the software package Abaqus. Following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The failure mechanism of the test specimens consisted of two stages: (i) yielding of the thin-walled web opening reinforcement or local web buckling in vicinity of the opening in case of a thick-walled reinforcement; (ii) global post-buckling.
2. In contrast to unperforated corrugated webs, the slope of the load-displacement curves decreases pronouncedly non-linearly for thin-walled web opening reinforcements as the ultimate load is approached due to plastic deformation of the reinforcement.
3. The analytical model in Section 2 predicts conservative ultimate loads for TCWG with reinforced square web openings. In particular, for thin-walled reinforcements, the analytical model delivers over-conservative results for the considered case.
4. The design rules of EN 1993-1-5, Annex D for unperforated TCWG can only be safely applied if the reinforcement of the web opening is sufficiently heavy.
5. The shear force resistance of TCWG with reinforced square web openings is not very sensitive to web imperfections if the reinforcement experienced plastic deformation at the ultimate load level.

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